

Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) safety and security aspects in the regulatory framework

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Abstract

Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) have become integral to various sectors, offering substantial benefits in efficiency and accessibility. However, their integration into civilian airspace presents significant safety and security challenges¹. This article examines the regulatory framework governing UAS operations, focusing on measures designed to mitigate risks. Key aspects include airspace management, pilot certification, and technological safeguards such as geofencing and remote identification. The regulatory landscape is analyzed in terms of its ability to address collision risks, unauthorized access, and potential misuse for malicious purposes. The study highlights the balance regulators must achieve between fostering innovation and ensuring public safety and security, proposing enhancements to current policies to better adapt to the rapidly evolving UAS technology.

Key words

¹ J. Anton, "Cybersecurity; an EASA perspective on developments and challenges", online: https://www.iata.org/whatwedo/workgroups/Documents/Paperless_Conference_2017/Day1/1100-1130_Cybersecurity_EASA.pdf, accessed on 23/02/2024.

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Safety aspects in the regulatory framework

The Convention on International Civil Aviation (hereinafter the "Chicago Convention"), although signed in 1944, so long before the BSP became popular, contained a provision relating to the principles of their use². We are talking about her art. 8 with the following wording: "An aircraft capable of flying without a pilot may fly without a pilot over the territory of a Contracting State only with the special authorization of that State and in accordance with the terms of such authorization. Each contracting State undertakes to ensure control of the flights of aircraft without a pilot in areas open to civil aircraft in such a way as to avoid danger to civil aircraft. " It is worth noting here that pursuant to Art. 8 unmanned ships are treated similarly to those with crew, insofar as in the case of each of them, a flight over the territory of a foreign country may take place only with its prior consent.

The provisions of the quoted Chicago Convention are subject to successive changes, which is directly related to the progressive development of aviation and the newly emerging technical and operational issues. As regards UAVs themselves, following A. Konert and P. Kasprzyk³, mention should be made of the changes to Annex 2 to the Chicago Convention, introducing to the definition of UAV a general requirement that UAV operations should be carried out in such a way as to minimize the risk to people, property and other aircraft, as well as the specification (in Appendix 4) of the requirements for issuing the authorization to perform a UAV crossing the state border⁴.

² ICAO, Convention on International Civil Aviation, signed at Chicago on 7 December 1944, ICAO Doc. 7300/9 (2006), online: https://www.icao.int/publications/Documents/7300_cons.pdf, accessed on 21/02/2024. The Chicago Convention came into force on 4 April 1947.

³ Konert A., Kasprzyk P., Drone Law. Future of Aviation Law? Peter Lang, 2023.

⁴ Konert A., Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne. Nowa era w prawie lotniczym. Zagadnienia cywilnoprawne, C.H. Beck, Warszawa 2020.

The Annex also distinguishes the functions related to the operation of the UAS into the following: remotely operated aircraft system operator, remotely operated aircraft pilot and remotely operated aircraft observer. Thus, an RVA operator is a person, organization or enterprise engaged in or intending to operate / use a remote control aircraft system, and a remote pilot is an authorized person. by the user to perform the duties essential to the operation of a remotely operated aircraft that properly controls the aircraft during its flight. Finally, the RPA observer is a trained competent person, designated by the operator, who, by visual observation of the remotely piloted aircraft, assists the pilot in the safe conduct of the flight. The said Appendix 4 to the Annex defines "Remotely piloted aircraft systems." It also confirms that an unmanned aerial vehicle is an aircraft and that, in principle, the provisions relating to manned ships (registration, unlawful taking, marking used, etc.) apply to it⁵.

Art. 12 of the Chicago Convention, which reads as follows: "Each Contracting State undertakes to take appropriate measures to ensure that any aircraft that flies over its territory or maneuvers within its territory, as well as any aircraft bearing its national emblem, regardless of place of in which it is located must comply with local rules and regulations relating to the flight and maneuvering of aircraft. Each contracting State undertakes to keep its own regulations in this field, to the greatest extent possible, consistent with the regulations established from time to time under this Convention. The rules established under this Convention shall apply to the high seas. Each contracting State undertakes to ensure the prosecution of all persons who break the applicable regulations. " As it results from the regulation, the tasks of each state-party to the Convention include establishing the internal flight regime in their airspace⁶. While in the case of cross-border civil commercial flights that are meticulously planned and prepared to comply with the rules of the air in the space of each state over whose territory a crewed aircraft is flown is a normal part of the flight plan, the situation may be difficult in the case of unmanned aerial vehicles. Well, users of drones using them for flights for recreational or professional purposes, but without transporting passengers (e.g. for filming or delivering goods), must also often face the fact that the

⁵ Skybrary, see definition of "unlawful interference", 2020, online: https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Unlawful_Interference, accessed on 21/05/2024.

⁶ Konert A., Kotliński M., "How come I cannot fly with the drone over the White House?" - Criminal and Civil Liability of the Drone Operator in Poland, *Ius Novum* nr 4/2018.

drone piloted / controlled by them crosses the state borders during the flight, hence it is already subject to a different legal regime, which also includes air traffic regulations. For many non-large-scale airline operators (such as airlines), this legal "fragmentation" can be highly embarrassing and thus discouraging the use of UAVs for cross-border operations. Hence the significant need to unify air traffic regulations, at least at the regional level⁷.

The European Union rightly treats the technological development of drones and their market potential as one of the strategic elements for the future of the Community's civil aviation, which is reflected in the "Aviation Strategy for Europe" published by the European Commission in 2015. This Communication discusses the importance of the aviation sector for the European economy and presents the challenges that the aviation market will face in the coming years. As far as the BSP market is concerned, the European Commission predicts that by 2035 this sector will be responsible for more than 100,000 jobs in Europe and generate revenues of € 10 billion, mainly in services. The EU Transport Commissioner for 2014-2019, Violeta Bulc herself said: "The EU will now have the most advanced rules in the world. This will pave the way for the safe flight of unmanned aerial vehicles. It will also provide much-needed transparency in the operation of the business sector and innovative drone companies across Europe"⁸.

European drone market has the potential to have a strong impact also on global markets. Of course, such a growing popularity of BSP among a wide group of recipients is associated with the need to adopt appropriate legal provisions. It is also important that the regulations issued in the European Union correspond not only to the realities present on the European continent, but also other regions of the world.

EU regulations must reconcile the interests of various states belonging to this organization. And in the case of drones, the expectations of other stakeholder groups also collide: manufacturers, users, various public and military services, as well as state authorities. All these factors influence the legislative process. With the popularization

⁷ B.I. Scott (ed.), "The law of unmanned aircraft systems. An introduction to the current and future regulation under national, regional and international law", Kluwer Law International BV, The Netherlands, 2016.

⁸ M. Geoff, E. Steuter, "Drone Nation: The Political Economy of America's New Way of War", 2016, p. 63.

of unmanned aerial vehicles, there is a need to optimally balance the benefits and challenges that this sector brings with it, and to introduce appropriate legal provisions taking into account the rapid pace of development of this sector.

The most important legal acts of the European Union in the field of unmanned aerial vehicles include, among others:

1. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 (hereinafter "Regulation 2019/945") of 12 March 2019 on unmanned aerial systems and operators of unmanned aerial systems of third countries.
2. Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 (hereinafter "Regulation 2019/947") of 24 May 2019 on the rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aerial vehicles.

Both legal acts provide definitions related to unmanned aerial vehicles. Regulation 2019/945 of March 12, 2019 states that "(...) unmanned aerial vehicle means any aircraft operated or intended to be operated without a pilot on board, which may operate autonomously or be piloted remotely." On the other hand, Regulation 2019/947 of May 24, 2019 extends the scope of the concept, taking into account that, apart from the unit itself, the unmanned aerial vehicle should also be understood as the equipment for remote control of the ship.

The new regulations entered into force, obliging Member States to adapt existing internal regulations to the new EU law⁹. The Union itself assumes that by June 2021 national regulations will be compatible with European Union law¹⁰. It is assumed that the overriding goal of introducing new regulations is, first of all, to ensure the common security of unmanned aerial vehicle operations and to protect the privacy of EU citizens, while allowing free access to the airspace for unmanned aerial vehicles. This is stated in the Preamble to Regulation 2019/947 in point 1: "Unmanned aerial

⁹ See ICAO, "Assembly Resolutions in Force", Doc 101140, online: https://www.icao.int/publications/Documents/10140_en.pdf, accessed on 21/02/2024.

¹⁰ M. Ostrihansky, M. Sakowska-Baryła, M. Szmigiero, The law of drones, Unmanned aircraft in European Union law, Warszawa 2021.

vehicles, regardless of their weight, may be operated within the single European airspace alongside manned aircraft, both airplanes and helicopters"¹¹.

From the point of view of air traffic and its safety, Art. 3 of Regulation 2019/947, which introduces three categories of UAS operations:

- "open" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 4 of the regulation;
- "specific" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 5 of the regulation;
- "certified" category, which means the UAS operation category as defined in Art. 6 of the Regulation.

Each of the categories included in the following articles introduces increasingly restrictive regulations regarding the use of drones in the airspace. To classify an operation as "open", it must cumulatively meet the following conditions:

- a) UAV belongs to one of the classes specified in Regulation 2019/945 or was constructed for private use, or meets the conditions specified in Art. 20;
- b) UAV has a maximum take-off mass of less than 25 kg;
- c) the UAV pilot ensures that the unmanned aerial vehicle maintains a safe distance from people and that its flight does not pass over assemblies of people;
- d) the UAV pilot keeps the unit within the visual range of the VLOS at all times (with a few exceptions referred to in the rule);
- e) during the flight, the UAV is kept at a distance of not more than 120 meters from the nearest point of the earth's surface, except when it is flying over an obstacle;
- f) during the flight, the UAV does not carry any hazardous materials, nor does it drop any materials.

If any of the above conditions is not met, then the operation is considered to be "special" and the operator must obtain prior approval from a state authority to perform it. However, an operation can be "certified" if:

- a) the UAV carrying it out falls under the "certified" category in accordance with Regulation 2019/945;

¹¹ R. Altawy, Amr. M. Youssef, "Security, privacy, and safety aspects of civilian drones: a survey", ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems, November 2016, pp. 1-25.

- b) is performed over assemblies of people;
- c) involves the carriage of passengers;
- d) involves the carriage of dangerous goods.

Further provisions of Regulation 2019/947 relate, inter alia, to the competence of pilots of unmanned ships, their minimum age, certification procedures, etc.

On the other hand, Regulation 2019/945 functions as an act regulating the design and production of UAVs intended for operation in accordance with the principles and conditions set out in Regulation 2019/947, as well as placing on the market and thus subjecting to free movement of drones operated under the "open" category. Finally, the Regulation's task is to establish the rules for the use of UAVs by operators from third countries (all this is laid down in Article 1). It can therefore be seen that, unlike Regulation 2019/947, whose task is primarily to create a framework for the safe use of all types of drones on the territory of EU countries, Regulation 2019/945 is intended to ensure that already at the production stage, and then introduced into the free market, these machines were safe and, where there was a high degree of risk of use, properly certified. Thus, the obligations set out in this Regulation are borne by entities such as producers, distributors or importers.

At the same time, the EU legislator should be appreciated for a fairly rational approach to the issue. Similarly, to Regulation 2019/947, this regulation also categorizes drone operations into "open", "special" and "certified", while imposing stricter certification obligations for those units whose operation is associated with a higher risk.

As the delegated regulations are directly applicable, no additional legal acts by the Member States will be required for their application.

It must be emphasized that with the publication of these regulations by the Commission there is no direct application of them, since EASA, the European Agency for Air Safety and the rest of the state agencies or competent bodies of each of the member states, they must publish the Acceptable Means of Compliance and the Guide

Material to make these regulations practical. Each of the regulations includes a period of entry into force, even differentiated by parts of them¹².

REGULATION 2019/945:

This regulation establishes the requirements for the design and manufacture of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS in regulation 2019/947). It also deals with the commercialization requirements of the UAS for an open category in Chapter II, including the systems or accessories that they must have. Chapter III is applicable to UAS for specific category and certified category, establishing its requirements in terms of design, production and maintenance and use according to the purposes. Chapter IV talks about the operations carried out by operators from third countries that are not from the European Union.

One of the most important parts of Regulation 2019/945 is Annex I, where the UAS classes are established. In response to its maximum take-off mass, the following classes are established:

- C0: MMD <250g;
- C1: MMD <900g;
- C2: MMD <4kg;
- C3: MMD <25kg;
- C4: MMD <25kg without automatic control modes, or model airplanes.

Each of the classes has a series of requirements for its manufacture and obtaining the CE marking, necessary for its commercialization in the EU. It is worth highlighting several novelties or curiosities:

- Height limitation system on the take-off point of the aircraft at 120m or above ground. If the height is selectable by the pilot, the system must have a reading of the height on the ground at all times, so as not to exceed the aforementioned limitation.
- Direct identification system that aircraft should have from class C1. A system that allows and guarantees, in accordance with the regulations, in real time during the entire duration of the flight, the direct periodic

¹² EASA, "High Level Conference Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation Krakow Declaration", 2017, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/DECLARATION-Krakow-Cybersecurity.pdf>, accessed on 23/02/2024.

dissemination of relevant information from the aircraft using an open and documented transmission protocol, including a unique registration number and data about the operator A system that will allow drones to be monitored in airspace along with 5G and IoT telecommunications technologies¹³.

There is also information about geoscience or geofencing systems, although they are not as novel and the drones already carry them. Although the current geoconscience systems (such as the DJI NFZ) do not use data from aeronautical information systems or aeronautical charts, as it does require that the new regulation must be made.

There is also information about the manuals and maintenance instructions that should have been prepared from UAV class C1.

Although the 2019/947 regulation establishes a transitory period of use for current equipment that does not comply with the previous requirements, in the Article 20 thereof, until 2022.

REGULATION 2019/947:

Regulation 2019/947 establishes the normal and regulations for the use of UAS in European airspace, which will come into force on July 1, 2020.

In the annex, OPEN-open, SPECIFIC-specific or CERTIFIED-certified operation categories are established.

For the Open category, the subcategories A1, A2 and A3 are established, depending on the type of operation, its area of flight and the type of aircraft used.

Subcategory A1 is established for drones of less than 250g or classes C0 or C1, avoiding flight over concentrations of people for classes C0 or less than 250g (if it does not meet the requirements of Regulation 2019/945) or about people for the class C1. For this category it will be necessary to know the equipment user manual as well as to have an online training course for class C1 aircraft.

The subcategory A2 establishes for aircraft of class C2, with the possibility of making flights of more than 30m horizontal distance over people (never over them) or up to 5m with the necessary precautions. The responsible drivers must have

¹³ P. Sienkiewicz, H. Świeboda, Sieci teleinformatyczne jako instrument państwa – zjawisko walki informacyjnej, in: Bezpieczeństwo teleinformatyczne państwa.

knowledge of the team's user manual, the online training course (which will be valid for 5 years), a self-study course and passing an exam carried out by the competent authority of each member state.

The subcategory A3 establishes the training conditions of the pilot as those of the subcategory A2 and the flight scenario should not be about people besides saving 150m with respect to populated areas. Aircraft of classes C2, C3, C4 or less than 25kg of maximum take-off mass may be used.

For flights in a specific category, the operator must have an operational authorization, which may be punctual for one or several operations or may have a CAA approval (light UAS operator certificate) as specified in Annex Part C. For this purpose, the operator must perform a risk assessment subject to the conditions set out in the regulations.

The competent authority will establish standard scenarios, specified in appendix 1, which will result in the operator not having to have an operational authorization but with a declaration, it is understood that under the declaration of responsible regime.

The regulation in article 15 establishes the operational conditions applicable to the geographical areas of the UAS for reasons of security, protection, privacy or environment. The member states are allowed the ability to prohibit, restrict or impose the specific conditions for each specific area, as established today with areas of controlled airspace, prohibited, restricted, dangerous or wildlife protection zones¹⁴.

Authorizations granted to UAS operators, certificates of competence of remote pilots and statements submitted by UAS operators or equivalent documentation, issued on the basis of national law, will remain valid until July 1, 2021. Member States shall, by 1 July 2021, convert their current remote pilot competence certificates and their authorizations or declarations of UAS operators, or equivalent documentation, including those issued up to that date, in accordance with this regulation.

In transitory dispositions the use of UAS in open category is also established, different to those contemplated in regulation 2019/945 until 2022, establishing its classification according to weight.

The new rules are an important step for the industry. The legislation defines the requirements for drone capabilities for achieving maximal safety. An example of such

¹⁴ T. Hamilton, D. Ochmanek, "Operating Low-Cost, Reusable Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Contested Environments" published by the RAND Corporation, Santa Monica, USA 2020.

a condition is ensuring an individual identification of every drone that will enable national authorities to better react to certain situations when necessary.

Moreover, the EU-wide rules provide unprecedented flexibility to both recreational and professional drone users. According to the laws, operators will be required to register their drones in the Member State where they reside or conduct business. Once pilots receive a permit from a European Union state, they will have the freedom to fly their drones across the whole EU.

Further EASA actions should be focused on the provision of materials to assist the involved parties in complying with the adopted legislation.

Security aspects in the regulatory framework

The UASs, under the international, regional, and national regime of aviation law, are considered as aircraft, therefore, the aviation cybersecurity framework should apply to their operations. High-level dependence on digital components and system communication makes UASs vulnerable to cyber threats¹⁵. Generally, the aviation cybersecurity framework is still in development and needs more attention^{16 17}.

The enhanced functionality of UASs and their modern technological advances, especially considering wireless communication interfaces, increased the scope of their potential usage. In general, the communication flow takes place between the drones mutually and between the drones and ground stations. Some of the commonly used forms of communication between drones and ground stations are Wi-Fi, GPS, Bluetooth, Infrared, and ZigBee, which are sensitive to attacks. Drones are connected to computers and networks, store many data, and transmit information¹⁸. Due to critical

¹⁵ Aleksandrowicz T., Strategie bezpieczeństwa w cyberprzestrzeni. Cyberwojny, w: Sieciocentryczne bezpieczeństwo. Wojna, pokój i terroryzm w epoce informacji, K. Liedel, P. Piasecka, T. Aleksandrowicz (red.), Warszawa 2014, Difin.

¹⁶ Homeland Security, National Protection and Programs Directorate, Office of Cyber and Infrastructure Analysis (OCIA), "Cybersecurity risks posed by unmanned aircraft systems", May 2018, online: <https://www.eisac.com/cartella/Asset/00007102/OCIA%20-%20Cybersecurity%20Risks%20Posed%20by%20Unmanned%20Aircraft%20Systems.pdf?parent=115994>, accessed on 20/02/2024.

¹⁷ D. F. Katz, J. Pringle, G. J. Guillot, "Cybersecurity for drones: don't fly blind", Lexology, November 2019.

¹⁸ United States Computer Emergency Readiness Team (US-CERT), "Securing Wireless Networks", 2016, online: www.us-cert.gov/ncas/tips/ST05-003, accessed on 19/05/2024.

information being part of that flow, the UASs are a very attractive target for malicious actors¹⁹.

Today, UAS's are devices whose use on the battlefield is constantly growing as well. But also their popularity increases the risk of destructive cyber-attacks that may affect complex networks and systems. In the report, RAND Corporation experts described the possible threats resulting from the use of drones during operations and presented recommendations, the implementation of which should realistically increase the level of cybersecurity of unmanned aerial systems²⁰.

In the world of constant and dynamic technological changes, minimizing vulnerability is an endless race with opponents, reads the report "How to Analyze the Cyber Threat from Drones" prepared by specialists from RAND Corporation. In the document, specialists analyzed the issue of cybersecurity in relation to the growing use of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS)²¹.

Experts indicate that today UAS have become more common, more accessible and more useful due to new possibilities, such as increased data collection capabilities and autonomous operation of operations. In this way, UAS can be both a target of a cyber-attack and an effective weapon.

The report presents the security implications of the rapid development of UAS technology, focusing in particular on vulnerabilities and future trends. "As UAS become more common, both the likelihood of a cyber-attack and the potential security implications are increasing," the document said. According to data presented by specialists, estimated UAS sales will exceed \$ 20 billion by the end of 2021²².

Experts also attempted to identify possible trends and potential consequences for operators. Specialists predict that drones will be even more integrated with security systems. New developments in UAS technology, including the introduction of more

¹⁹ R. Doss, S. Piramuthu, W. Zhou, "Future Network Systems and Security: 5th International Conference, FNSS 2019, Melbourne, VIC, Australia, November 27–29, 2019, Proceedings".

²⁰ M.H. Au, S.M. Yiu, J. Li, X. Luo, C. Wang, A. Castiglione, K. Kluczniak, "Network and System Security: 12th International Conference, NSS 2018, Hong Kong, China, August 27-29, 2018, Proceedings".

²¹ Pyzynski M., Balcerzak T. (2020), Cybersecurity of the Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS), REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVEGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica): 2386-8902, ISSN (versión impresa): 1130-2127 Depósito legal: Z-3235-99 Malaga.

²² The Economist, "Technology Quarterly: Taking Flight", 2017, online: www.economist.com/technology-quarterly/2017-06-08/civilian-drones, accessed on 20/02/2024.

autonomous control software and the ability to create a swarm of drones via mobile networks, increase the scope and advancement of potential cyber-attacks.

The report shows that entities using UAS may become victims of cyber-attacks, including data breach incidents. This is due to the fact that the control of these devices takes place from a location center located in a specific place on earth. This is where sensitive data and wireless networks are found that are attractive to hackers. Moreover, specialists have no doubts that "UAS controllers exhibit vulnerabilities and are therefore an access point for malicious actors".

Experts emphasize that the incident does not have to be carried out using the targeted networks and systems directly related to the device. They indicate that hackers can use, inter alia, the private equipment of the drone operator, which, for example, logs into a specific network responsible for UAS settings.

RAND Corporation experts clearly indicate that the attacked drones may affect the security of the US Department of Homeland Security. Experts explain that the incident can effectively limit the intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance capabilities of the services and thus contribute to the development of crime²³.

It is also alarming that an advanced cyberattack against the equipment used by the American Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) is possible. The drones at the agency's disposal can be "hijacked" by hackers and used to directly destroy elements of critical infrastructure²⁴.

Moreover, a cyberattack on UAS systems used by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) may reduce the agency's ability to identify vulnerable areas and people in danger or health, warn RAND Corporation specialists²⁵.

The report also includes recommendations, the implementation of which should really contribute to increasing the cybersecurity of drones and related networks and systems. Experts indicate that the first step to protect against cyberattacks against UAS

²³ D. Barnhizer, D. Barnhizer, "The Artificial Intelligence Contagion: Can Democracy Withstand the Imminent Transformation of Work, Wealth and the Social Order?", 2019.

²⁴ Balcerzak T., Kostur-Balcerzak K., Żmigrodzka M., (2019), Cybersecurity in civil aviation, Bezpieczeństwo w międzynarodowym i krajowym prawie lotniczym i kosmicznym, ISBN: 978-83-7996-752-0.

²⁵ E. Lichocki, Model systemu zarządzania kryzysowego w warunkach zagrożeń cyberterrorystycznych dla bezpieczeństwa informacyjnego Sił Zbrojnych RP, Wydział Bezpieczeństwa Narodowego Akademii Obrony Narodowej, Warszawa 2009.

should be primarily to create a map of threatened areas and to create an effective risk neutralization plan. It is also necessary to establish cooperation with cybersecurity specialists who have appropriate experience and knowledge to improve the quality of security. At the state level, the priority seems to be to tighten the relationship between state administration entities and law enforcement agencies in order to create a common cyberstrategy dedicated to UAS.

It is equally important to invest in regular testing of equipment in cross-sectoral cooperation (state, private companies, laboratories, research centers, etc.), as it enables the creation of universal security and protection protocols that could be implemented on a larger scale.

The key element is also the identification of security gaps and taking effective actions to eliminate them. In this regard, it is necessary to constantly monitor UAS systems and follow the development of this technology. The "coordinated and constantly updated system of monitoring and intervention seems to be indispensable, because even the latest solutions do not guarantee full resistance to every cyber-attack".

Moreover, experts indicate that in addition, the possible consequences of the spread of UAS technology should be anticipated. "As drones are used in a wider range of activities, the number of lawful uses of UAS at any given time will increase," the report reads. - "Therefore, from the point of view of risk reduction, one of the most important tasks in the area of UAS operation will be to distinguish and define legal operations from illegal activities using drones".

It needs to be noted that even if there is a lot of advantages of using drones, they remain vulnerable, as there is no pilot onboard to monitor any unusual situations during their operations. As there is no manual control, it is possible to gain access to data for the malicious actors and insert fraudulent information into drones. This may result in reprogramming drones, doing irreversible damage, or even taking full control over them.

Cyber attackers, utilizing the UASs, can potentially exploit points of access, unsecured networks, or other devices wirelessly. By doing so, the malicious actors may be able to execute malicious code, inject malware, perform a man-in-the-middle attack, and much more. It is also possible that a drone can be hacked by using another drone, which can be possible by using a Wi-Fi network. For example, in 2014, researches from

Sensepoint security firm developed an application that was installed on a drone. Through an open Wi-Fi network, a flying drone with that application was able to steal users' data, like usernames, passwords, credit card details, from devices connected to the network.

As another example, security analysts claimed and proved the ability to hijack and even take control over a drone mid-flight. By hijacking a drone, the malicious actor can potentially extract data related to the flight route, gain access to pictures and videos taken during the flight, as well as control the movement of a drone, ultimately having an impact on public safety as well as the safety of the manned aircraft and its personnel. Accessing the data stored on the drone is critical and may endanger the security of any personal data and privacy of the user²⁶.

The security concerns related to drones and their dependency on GPS need to be addressed. As GPS is used for drones' navigation and as there is no encryption in place, it is an easy target for attackers. Losing control of drones by a GPS spoofing attack may result in massive harm²⁷. For example, it was claimed that in December 2011, Iranian forces took control over a Lockheed Martin RQ-170 Sentinel drone, which belonged to the United States Air Force. The explanation of taking control of a drone was a potential GPS spoofing attack.

However, there are no confirmed incidents of exploiting wireless systems by using drones; the research community was able to demonstrate such a possibility. In 2015, researchers from Singapore, using 3G or 4G connection with a smartphone being attached to a drone and having installed applications with the ability to detect printers connected to unsecured wireless networks, were able to intercept a document sent to a printer and save a copy. The document was still sent for printing; thus, the document owner was not aware of the attack. The claim of other researchers in 2016 was related to the compromising of smart lightbulbs inside the building by a piece of equipment attached to a drone. The attack was performed by flying a drone at a range of 350 meters to take control of the lightbulbs by firmware updates²⁸.

²⁶ E. Vattapparamban, I. Güvenç, A. I. Yurekli, K. Akkaya and S. Uluagaç, "Drones for smart cities: Issues in cybersecurity, privacy, and public safety," 2016 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC), Paphos, 2016, pp. 216-221.

²⁷ ICAO, Twelfth Air Navigation Conference, online: ICAO <https://www.icao.int/Meetings/anconf12/pages/default.aspx>, accessed on 21/02/2024.

²⁸ E. Nowak, M. Nowak, Zarys teorii bezpieczeństwa narodowego, Warszawa 2011.

Taking into consideration the requirements for the manufacturers to ensure the systems built into the UAS are secure and cannot be exploited by the users, the malicious actors still find a way to perform an attack. Moreover, it needs to be considered that there is a huge number of drones with outdated security controls or so-called self-assembled drones without the required level of security controls, posing a high risk.

Cyber threats related to the operation of UASs are continually evolving with the development of technology, a higher level of digitization, and expanding capabilities of drones²⁹.

Cyberspace has also become an environment of combat and war. In this context, it is necessary to emphasize the problem of the international legal assessment of the means of information warfare waged in this space. Its rank and importance - for example in the case of technological development and the increasing importance of digital information - will increase in the foreseeable future³⁰. Several elements should be mentioned here. Firstly, there is no doubt that information warfare in cyberspace within the framework of the ongoing armed conflict is an inherent part of this conflict. Secondly, information warfare waged in cyberspace spontaneously, i.e. in conditions of peace - without military operations, is gaining more and more importance³¹. In such a fight, the objectives do not have a direct military significance (as, for example, in an armed conflict, cyber-attacks on the enemy's command and communication systems), but belong to the category of the state's critical infrastructure. Such attacks may cause threats to international security (global information security), destabilization of critical infrastructure, disruptions in the functioning of public administration, economic losses (inhibition of the development of companies and enterprises) or even personal losses of citizens. The scale of the attack and the losses are important³².

²⁹ M. Pyzynski, "Current approach to secure the civil aviation industry against cyber threats", *Prawo a nowoczesność. Wyzwania – problemy – nadzieje*, Warsaw 2019, pp. 219-229.

³⁰ J. Yu-Min, T. Teck-Boon Tan, "Smart Cities: A New Age of Digital Insecurity, Survival", Volume 60, 2018, pp. 91-106.

³¹ B. Pacek, R. Hoffman, *Działania sił zbrojnych w cyberprzestrzeni*, Warszawa 2013.

³² The National Strategy to Secure Cyberspace [online], February 2003, <http://www.hsd1.org/?view&-did=1040>, accessed on 25/04/2024

Third, cyberspace is used by criminals acting only for profit. This aspect has been discussed above³³.

The fact remains that the problem of self-contained information warfare in cyberspace is not at all referred to in the applicable international law. When analyzing hypothetical cyber-attacks on the state's critical infrastructure, the following situations can be identified:

- the attacker is known and the state (victim) takes military action against him,
- in a similar situation, the state (the victim) responds with a cyber-attack on the aggressor's infrastructure,
- the attacker is unknown, it is possible to identify only the IP address, and the attacked country, using hacking tools, takes control of the hard disk and, for example, destroys the data stored there,
- the attacker is not identified at all, which means that the state (the victim) does not know by whom he was attacked and does not know who to retaliate against.

Military responses to cyber-attacks are already envisaged in states' strategies. For example, the United States reserves the right to respond to such threats by all necessary and appropriate means. In Polish legislation, attacks from cyberspace were treated on a par with an armed attack on the territory of the Republic of Poland or terrorist attacks as an external threat to the state justifying the introduction of martial law³⁴.

While the case of Poland is beyond dispute (the introduction of martial law does not mean taking military action), the possibility of taking a strictly military or only cybernetic retaliation raises doubts. It is not clear (at least it does not emphatically result from the applicable international law) whether a cyber-attack on critical infrastructure can be considered a justification for taking actions under Art. 51 of the United Nations Charter (self-defense), and therefore - military actions in self-defense. Undoubtedly, it would have to be a serious attack, i.e. not an incident, but an action involving significant losses in the material sphere and human casualties (e.g. leading to an explosion of a

³³ Osiecki M., Fortońska A., Książek-Janik E., Criminal liability for unlawful usage of unmanned aircraft vehicles in selected countries of the world. 2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS), 903-910.

³⁴ Konert A., Kotliński M., Polish regulations on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, *Transportation Research Procedia* Volume 35, 2018.

nuclear power plant)³⁵. The consequence of this would be to consider such an attack an armed attack, or at least a threat to international peace and security³⁶. As it stands today, only the United Nations Security Council could do so, as it happened after the terrorist attacks on September 11, 2001³⁷.

The attacked state's reaction to launch a retaliatory cyber-attack would belong to the so-called countermeasures, formerly known as repressions. When applying them, the principle of proportionality of the retaliatory measure to the infringement committed and the aim pursued should be respected, and the aggrieved State should make a claim for reparation before launching them. The doctrine of international law emphasizes that repression as a retaliatory measure consists in a temporary suspension of the application of a specific rule of international law by the aggrieved state, undertaken in response to actions contrary to the international law of another state. Under normal circumstances, measures used as repressive measures are in conflict with international law, and only the prior action of another state justifies retaliation against them. The applied repression may not, however, violate the prohibition of the threat or use of force, fundamental human rights, humanitarian obligations and other obligations resulting from peremptory norms (i.e. norms of the "ius cogens" type, which are absolutely binding) of general international law.

The third case of a hypothetical attack is extremely difficult to classify under international law. Such an attack would rather be a conventional offense, and the state's reaction described above is very difficult to classify under international law.

The issues raised require urgent solutions. It is difficult to accept the dictatorship of the forces that do not recognize any rules of conflict, including armed ones. It is also difficult to allow a situation in which states are forced to break applicable international law. The application of the principle of "necessity does not know the law", mentioned several times, is a straightforward way to degrade the role of international law and thus - to anarchize international relations. This rule can only be considered as an exception

³⁵ Osiecki M., *International Legal Aspects of Aerial Terrorism. Methods of Law Enforcement in Aviation*, Peter Lang Publishing (2002) Berlin, pp. 86-93.

³⁶ Żmigrodzka M.(2022) Opportunities and Threats to Services using Unmanned Aerial Systems, *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, eISSN2395-6518.

³⁷ Osiecki M., Fortońska, A., Berus, M. et al. Drone as a Target of Terrorist Attack and a Weapon Against Terrorism – Analysis in the Light of International Law. *J Intell Robot Syst* 106, 6 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-022-01712-2>.

in emergency situations requiring a quick and decisive solution. However, it should never be included in the set of fundamental principles of international law³⁸.

As stated hereinbefore, the UAS is considered an aircraft; therefore, the rules on cybersecurity-related to civil aviation should also apply to the UAS. However, it should be noted that due to the unique capabilities of drones, equal or even higher requirements should be put in place to protect their systems against cyber-attacks. Referring to the framework of the civil aviation cybersecurity framework, it needs to be underlined that the actions against cyber threats have already been initiated, and their development is continuous at international and regional (the European Union) levels.

Acts or attempted acts within the civil aviation that jeopardize the safety of flight are called acts of unlawful interference. The catalog of acts of unlawful interference is defined by the Annex 17 to the Chicago Convention. It needs to be noted that this catalog is non-exhaustive; therefore, a potential act committed by any cyber means should be included within the scope of that definition³⁹.

Civil aviation is protected against acts of unlawful interference by international conventions. The first convention indirectly refers to cyber-attacks is the Beijing Convention of 2010. Article 1 d) of the Beijing Convention states this is when a person unlawfully and intentionally “destroys or damages air navigation facilities or interferes with their operation, if any such act is likely to endanger the safety of aircraft in flight.” Article 1 e) of that convention states also that an offense is committed by communications of false information to endanger the safety of an aircraft⁴⁰. This could refer to any act aiming at disruption through air navigation services. The mentioned provisions unquestionably apply, inter alia, to cyberattacks; however, they solely identify the offenses against the safety of airborne aircraft. Moreover, the Beijing Protocol of 2010, which supplements the Beijing Convention, states in Article 1 that “any person commits an offense if that person unlawfully and intentionally seizes or exercises control of an aircraft in service by force or threat thereof, or by coercion, or by any other form

³⁸ Kostur K., Żmigrodzka M., Balcerzak T. (2020), Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne w ochronie przeciwpożarowej, Unmanned aerial vehicles in fire protection, REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVEGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica).

³⁹ ICAO, Annex 17 to the Convention on Civil Aviation, Security: Safeguarding International Civil Aviation Against Acts of Unlawful Interference, 10th edition, Amendment 16, 2018.

⁴⁰ Beijing Protocol 2010, Supplementary to the convention for the suppression of unlawful seizure of aircraft, online: https://www.icao.int/secretariat/legal/Docs/beijing_protocol_multi.pdf accessed on 21/02/2024.

of intimidation, or by any technological means”. The abovementioned interpretative study regrettably proves that none of the international conventions directly address cyber offenses against civil aviation⁴¹.

Significant step towards the development of the civil cybersecurity framework is the work of the leading organizations at the international level as well as open dialogue and collaboration. It needs to be noted that the civil aviation legal regime is regulated by the Chicago Convention of 1944. Based on the Chicago Convention, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) was established with the primary aim to address principles for international air navigation and assist states in developing international air transport. Moreover, ICAO is responsible for implementing new regulations, standards, and best practices as well as changing existing ones. Therefore, the ICAO should retain leadership over the implementation of rules related to cybersecurity.

In 2012, during the ICAO Twelfth Air Navigation Conference (AN-Conf/12), a recommendation was put forward that the ICAO should take action and establish appropriate mechanisms to evaluate the scope of cybersecurity issues. At this time, the recommendation was related only to cyberterrorism.

In 2014, the ICAO adopted two recommendations within Annex 17 to address cybersecurity aspects. Following these developments, in 2018, the 16th amendment of Annex 17 delivered measures related to cybersecurity through standard 4.9.1. This is the only standard within the ICAO framework that addresses cybersecurity. It is followed by recommendation 4.9.2.

The Assembly Resolution A39-19 of 2016 called on the ICAO member states and industry stakeholders to represent a coordinated approach towards cybersecurity through strategies, policies, and information sharing. This coordination aimed to enable the identification of vulnerabilities⁴².

In order to coordinate the plan, ICAO established the Secretariat Study Group on Cybersecurity (SSGC) and related working groups to address cybersecurity issues

⁴¹ R. Abeyrante, “The Beijing Convention of 2010 on the suppression of unlawful acts relating to international civil aviation – an interpretative study”, *Journal of Transportation Security*, 2011, Volume 4 (2), p.132.

⁴² ICAO, Assembly Resolution, Addressing Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation, Appendix A39-ICAO Doc. WP/17 EX/5 30/5/16, 2016.

within civil aviation. It needs to be highlighted that through the work of SSGC, ICAO collaborates with the leading industry stakeholders to develop necessary provisions for cybersecurity. The outcomes of SSGC activity are satisfactory, especially when facilitating high-level discussions, exchanges of views, and ways to enhance international collaboration.

During the ICAO Assembly 40th Session in 2019, the current efforts of ICAO and its SSGC working group were commended by the Assembly, mainly through the endorsement of the ICAO Aviation Cybersecurity Strategy⁴³. It was underlined that it is essential to develop an action plan for strategy implementation. Following the above outcomes, the ICAO was instructed to develop an action plan. The objective of the action plan is to support member states and industry in the process of adopting the Aviation Cyber Security Strategy. Moreover, ICAO was called to conduct a feasibility study and a gap analysis that will be considered by the Council in order to define the most appropriate structure for ICAO to address cybersecurity within civil aviation.

At the European level, responsibility, in terms of the cybersecurity rulemaking process within civil aviation, is with the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA)⁴⁴. To ensure that civil aviation is protected against cyberthreats, EASA advocates for the development of the resilient, safe, and secure European aviation system⁴⁵. This process includes cybersecurity⁴⁶.

Following the recommendations from the high-level meeting on cybersecurity in civil aviation that was held in 2017, the European Strategic Coordination Platform (ESCP) was established to coordinate the cybersecurity approach at the European level and ensure the civil aviation system is resilient to cyber threats⁴⁷. Another objective of the ESCP is to ensure that future cyber threats are sufficiently managed. This is

⁴³ ICAO, "Aviation Cybersecurity Strategy", October 2019, online: <https://www.icao.int/cybersecurity/Documents/AVIATION%20CYBERSECURITY%20STRATEGY.EN.pdf>, accessed on 21/02/2024.

⁴⁴ EASA, The European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS) 2018-2022, 2017, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/EASA%20MB%20Decision%2008-2017%20Annex%201%20EPAS%202018-2022.pdf>, accessed on 22/02/2024.

⁴⁵ Konert A., Odpowiedzialność operatora bezzałogowego statku powietrznego za opóźnienie lub odwołanie lotu, *Ius Novum* 1/2021.

⁴⁶ F. Coman-Kund, "European Union Agencies as Global Actors: A Legal Study of the European Aviation Safety Agency, Frontex and Europol", London and New York: Routledge Tylor & Francis Group, 2018, pp. 120-123.

⁴⁷ EASA, "High Level Meeting: Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation", 2016

addressed by collaboration on the civil aviation cybersecurity framework and strategy⁴⁸. The ESCP established the Shared Trans-Organizational Risk Management (STORM) to guide the organizations in developing a methodology for risk management. The outcome of ESCP work is the development of the Strategy for Cybersecurity in Aviation that was published in 2019⁴⁹.

In 2018, based on the recommendation defined in the Krakow Declaration, the Regulation (EU) 216/2008 was replaced by a new Basic Regulation, i.e., Regulation (EU) 2018/1139. This was the first time; the Basic Regulation referred directly to cybersecurity and gave a coordinating role to collaborate with the industry stakeholder to EASA⁵⁰.

Additionally, due to the new regulation, EASA developed some rulemaking activities. This refers to the Aircraft Cybersecurity rulemaking activity (RMT.0648), which intends to address cybersecurity provisions through different certification specifications in order to mitigate cyber threats potentially impacting safety, as a consequence of intentional and unauthorized acts of interference to aircraft's networks and systems. Another rulemaking activity aims to introduce the provisions for the Management of information security risks (RMT.0720) related to the aeronautical information systems that are used in the civil aviation industry.

During the last High-Level Cybersecurity Conference co-organized by EASA at the Spanish CAA, that was held in March 2020 in Madrid, it was highlighted that the civil aviation stakeholders need to work collaboratively in order to avoid duplications, as well as it is crucial to bring together the security and safety experts to discuss together cybersecurity issues, educate on each other's domains and exchange the information.

⁴⁸ ESCP, "Strategy for cybersecurity in aviation", 2019, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/Cybersecurity%20St>, accessed on 24/02/2024.

⁴⁹ C. Rani, H. Modares, R. Sriram, D. Mikulski, F. Lewis, "Security of unmanned aerial vehicle systems against cyber-physical attacks", *The Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 2015.

⁵⁰ EUR-Lex, Regulation (EU) 2018/1139 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2018 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Union Aviation Safety Agency, and amending Regulations (EC) No 2111/2005, (EC) No 1008/2008, (EU) No 996/2010, (EU) No 376/2014 and Directives 2014/30/EU and 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 552/2004 and (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Regulation (EEC) No 3922/91.

The discussion also concluded that the organizations involved in the subject of cybersecurity need to address the sharing of information further and to build trust⁵¹.

The civil aviation industry and UAS industry need to be aware of the different threats coming from the usage of drones, especially taking into consideration UASs' integration into the airspace. It should be ensured that their integration will be performed efficiently and safely. As was mentioned, the continuous technology development and enhanced functionalities built into drones create new threat vectors that malicious actors will try to exploit. However, the framework of aviation cybersecurity is developing; a higher level of awareness of UASs is required in order to take action before their integration into airspace. Therefore, to facilitate that process, some further steps need to be considered.

First of all, the industry needs to make sure that the common level of understanding in terms of cyber threats, potential malicious actors, and their motivation exist across the stakeholders. Further research, communication, and workshops may help to achieve the same level of understanding to address cyber risks coherently. This may be useful for the development of a catalog of already experienced as well as potential threats. Having that knowledge may drive the development of countermeasures against future attacks.

Linked to the above, there is a need for an open dialogue among UAS manufacturers on how to secure the systems to ensure that their integration into the airspace will not pose cyber risks. This needs to be followed by a dialogue with the civil aviation industry and key international organizations to establish the proper trusted lines of communication as well as collaboration.

Once the desired maturity of understating is achieved, there is comprehensive knowledge of potential threats and malicious actors, and the lines of communication are established between the aviation industry and UAS stakeholders, the problem of UAS cybersecurity needs to be addressed with regulators to ensure that the legal framework is developed in a smart way. However, doing so requires that the regulators have sufficient knowledge of UASs, their system architecture, security controls, and potential

⁵¹ J. Rasmussen, EASA, "Conclusions of High Level Cybersecurity Conference", 2020, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/newsroom-and-events/events/2020-high-level-cybersecurity-conference>, accessed on 19/05/2024.

cyber threats, to establish the legal requirements for users to protect their systems. This requires the close collaboration of regulators with the UAS manufacturers.

As part of the rulemaking, better regulations are needed to define cybersecurity for drones. Rules for UASs do not explicitly specify provisions for cybersecurity. Moreover, implementing regulatory restrictions on the usage of drones should be considered by the manufacturers and regulators together.

As far as personal data is concerned, their confidentiality needs to be ensured and be protected against cyberattacks. The malicious actors, as stated in the previous section of this document, use drones to breach security and privacy to steal personal data. The current legal framework and regulators' awareness do not represent a sufficient level of protection. The only option is to undertake the required steps to address these issues and establish preventive measures⁵².

Another step that should be considered is the establishment of mechanisms for information sharing across UASs and civil aviation stakeholders. The type of information that needs to be shared should be defined. Potentially, a mechanism can be used to share information on new vulnerabilities in the systems, experienced cyberattacks, and lessons learned.

A consideration of the next steps to take to prevent future cyberattacks must not underestimate the role of education. There is a need for appropriate training programs for the users of the UASs. Undoubtedly, the syllabus should include the cyber risks related to the drones' operation and preventive measures to have in place. One of the solutions is to secure the networks and devices that can diminish the likelihood of malicious actors exploiting vulnerabilities and compromising systems. Users should be taught mitigation options, such as the importance of installing required updates and patches, changing passwords regularly, encrypting stored data, and restricting access. Layered security measures can potentially slow the attack and allow the user to detect and mitigate it on time⁵³.

⁵² Konert A., Przetwarzanie danych osobowych przez operatorów bezzałogowych statków powietrznych, *Ius Novum* 2/2021.

⁵³ H. Sedjelmaci, S. M. Senouci and M. Messous, "How to detect cyber-attacks in unmanned aerial vehicles network?", 2016 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), Washington, DC, 2016, pp. 1-6.

All of the steps above are a crucial part of raising the awareness of cyber threats and a part of building cybersecurity culture across the UAS's users, manufacturers, and the civil aviation industry. Without having that knowledge and without having established proper and trusted lines for collaboration, the above will be difficult to achieve, taking into consideration the emerging cyber threats in the continuously expanding UAS threat vector.

There is no perfect cybersecurity solution for the industry; however, there are a significant number of ways to detect and mitigate cyber risk. All of the steps discussed in this section are the basic ones. Taking the right actions now may help to complement the current aviation cybersecurity framework with the necessary provisions on the cybersecurity of UAS. It is crucial to ensure that the integrity of the UAS in the airspace is secured and protected against cyber-attacks.

The emergence and development of the information society brought - apart from indisputable benefits - also many threats to the security of the state and its citizens. Most of them are related to the development of cyberspace, as well as to the increasing and nowadays essential role of information, understood as a strategic resource. It is no wonder then that these threats fall into the category of information warfare.

This creates new challenges for the services responsible for state security. When undertaking information warfare in cyberspace, they must have both defensive and offensive abilities, and therefore - in other words - also the ability to deter a potential attacker, regardless of whether we are dealing with a cyber attack by the state, non-state entity or against the crime of espionage in cyberspace, or we are dealing with a criminal using modern communication technologies.

In a world of rapidly growing technology and with an increasing number of interconnected devices, cybersecurity is a crucial challenge, especially for the continuously expanding market of drones. Taking into consideration the broad spectrum of threats, the growing numbers of malicious actors, and the functionality enhancement of drones, the likelihood of cyber-attack against the UAS is huge. As it was discussed, there are different possibilities for the malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities with the UAS and perform a successful attack.

Taking into consideration that, according to the current regime of air law, the UASs are treated as aircraft, and since there is no specific cybersecurity framework

worldwide, the civil aviation framework should apply. Therefore, the alignment of both industries, UAS and civil aviation, in terms of a global approach against cyber threats, is highly important.

At international and regional (the European Union) levels, the leading organizations and industry stakeholders face a challenge in terms of cybersecurity. However, it needs to be underlined that the civil aviation cybersecurity framework is continuously developing, including rulemaking activities. However, there is still a significant number of actions to be done, especially considering the efficient and safe integration of the UAS into the airspace. In this regard, the cybersecurity of UAS needs to be further addressed within the scope of the existing civil aviation cybersecurity framework.

Conclusion

The integration of Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) into civilian airspace presents both opportunities and challenges, necessitating a robust regulatory framework to ensure safety and security⁵⁴. This article has explored the existing regulatory measures, including airspace management, pilot certification, and technological safeguards like geofencing and remote identification. The Chicago Convention, with its evolving provisions, underscores the need for comprehensive regulation of UAS operations to mitigate risks to people, property, and other aircraft.

The analysis highlights that while the regulatory framework has made significant strides in addressing the safety and security concerns of UAS operations, there are still areas requiring enhancement. The rapid technological advancements in UAS demand continuous updates to regulations to keep pace with new capabilities and potential threats. The European Union's proactive approach, through regulations such as EU 2019/945 and EU 2019/947, sets a benchmark for global standards, aiming to harmonize regulations across member states and ensure the safe integration of UAS into shared airspace.

Moving forward, it is imperative that regulators balance the promotion of innovation with the need to safeguard public safety and security. This includes

⁵⁴ M. Huttunen, "Civil unmanned aircraft systems and security: The European approach", *Journal of Transportation Security*, September 2019, p.1.

fostering international collaboration to unify air traffic regulations, thereby facilitating the safe and efficient operation of UAS across borders. By continually adapting regulatory frameworks to the evolving UAS landscape, authorities can better manage risks and leverage the full potential of UAS technology for various civilian applications.

The regulatory framework for UAS must be dynamic and responsive, addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by these systems. Through vigilant oversight and strategic policy enhancements, regulators can ensure that the integration of UAS into civilian airspace is both safe and beneficial, paving the way for the future of aviation.

References

- [1] Homeland Security, National Protection and Programs Directorate, Office of Cyber and Infrastructure Analysis (OCIA), "Cybersecurity risks posed by unmanned aircraft systems", May 2018, online: <https://www.eisac.com/cartella/Asset/00007102/OCIA%20-%20Cybersecurity%20Risks%20Posed%20by%20Unmanned%20Aircraft%20Systems.pdf?parent=115994>, accessed on 20/02/2024.
- [2] M. Huttunen, "Civil unmanned aircraft systems and security: The European approach", *Journal of Transportation Security*, September 2019, p.1.
- [3] D. F. Katz, J. Pringle, G. J. Guillot, "Cybersecurity for drones: don't fly blind", *Lexology*, November 2019.
- [4] *The Economist*, "Technology Quarterly: Taking Flight", 2017, online: www.economist.com/technology-quarterly/2017-06-08/civilian-drones, accessed on 20/02/2024.
- [5] E. Vattapparamban, I. Güvenç, A. I. Yurekli, K. Akkaya and S. Uluagaç, "Drones for smart cities: Issues in cybersecurity, privacy, and public safety," 2016 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC), Paphos, 2016, pp. 216-221.
- [6] R. Altawy, Amr. M. Youssef, "Security, privacy, and safety aspects of civilian drones: a survey", *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, November 2016, pp. 1-25.
- [7] H. Sedjelmaci, S. M. Senouci and M. Messous, "How to detect cyber-attacks in unmanned aerial vehicles network?", 2016 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), Washington, DC, 2016, pp. 1-6.

- [8] B.I. Scott (ed.), "The law of unmanned aircraft systems. An introduction to the current and future regulation under national, regional and international law", Kluwer Law International BV, The Netherlands, 2016.
- [9] R. Doss, S. Piramuthu, W. Zhou, "Future Network Systems and Security: 5th International Conference, FNSS 2019, Melbourne, VIC, Australia, November 27–29, 2019, Proceedings".
- [10] C. Rani, H. Modares, R. Sriram, D. Mikulski, F. Lewis, "Security of unmanned aerial vehicle systems against cyber-physical attacks", *The Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 2015.
- [11] M. Geoff, E. Steuter, "Drone Nation: The Political Economy of America's New Way of War", 2016, p. 63.
- [12] M.H. Au, S.M. Yiu, J. Li, X. Luo, C. Wang, A. Castiglione, K. Kluczniak, "Network and System Security: 12th International Conference, NSS 2018, Hong Kong, China, August 27-29, 2018, Proceedings".
- [13] J. Yu-Min, T. Teck-Boon Tan, "Smart Cities: A New Age of Digital Insecurity, Survival", Volume 60, 2018, pp. 91-106.
- [14] D. Barnhizer, D. Barnhizer, "The Artificial Intelligence Contagion: Can Democracy Withstand the Imminent Transformation of Work, Wealth and the Social Order?", 2019.
- [15] Skybrary, see definition of "unlawful interference", 2020, online: [https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Unlawful Interference](https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Unlawful_Interference), accessed on 21/05/2024.
- [16] R. Abeyrante, "The Beijing Convention of 2010 on the suppression of unlawful acts relating to international civil aviation – an interpretative study", *Journal of Transportation Security*, 2011, Volume 4 (2), p.132.
- [17] Beijing Protocol 2010, Supplementary to the convention for the suppression of unlawful seizure of aircraft, online: https://www.icao.int/secretariat/legal/Docs/beijing_protocol_multi.pdf accessed on 21/02/2024.
- [18] ICAO, Convention on International Civil Aviation, signed at Chicago on 7 December 1944, ICAO Doc. 7300/9 (2006), online: https://www.icao.int/publications/Documents/7300_cons.pdf, accessed on 21/02/2024. The Chicago Convention came into force on 4 April 1947.

- [19] ICAO, Twelfth Air Navigation Conference, online: <https://www.icao.int/Meetings/anconf12/pages/default.aspx>, accessed on 21/02/2024.
- [20] ICAO, Annex 17 to the Convention on Civil Aviation, Security: Safeguarding International Civil Aviation Against Acts of Unlawful Interference, 10th edition, Amendment 16, 2018.
- [21] ICAO, Assembly Resolution, Addressing Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation, Appendix A39-ICAO Doc. WP/17 EX/5 30/5/16, 2016.
- [22] M. Pyzynski, "Current approach to secure the civil aviation industry against cyber threats", *Prawo a nowoczesność. Wyzwania – problemy – nadzieje*, Warsaw 2019, pp. 219-229.
- [23] ICAO, "Aviation Cybersecurity Strategy", October 2019, online: <https://www.icao.int/cybersecurity/Documents/AVIATION%20CYBERSECURITY%20STRATEGY.EN.pdf>, accessed on 21/02/2024.
- [24] See ICAO, "Assembly Resolutions in Force", Doc 101140, online: https://www.icao.int/publications/Documents/101140_en.pdf, accessed on 21/02/2024.
- [25] F. Coman-Kund, "European Union Agencies as Global Actors: A Legal Study of the European Aviation Safety Agency, Frontex and Europol", London and New York: Routledge Tylor & Francis Group, 2018, pp. 120-123.
- [26] EASA, "High Level Meeting: Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation", 2016.
- [27] ESCP, "Strategy for cybersecurity in aviation", 2019, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/Cybersecurity%20St>, accessed on 24/02/2024.
- [28] EASA, "High Level Conference Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation Krakow Declaration", 2017, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/DECLARATION-Krakow-Cybersecurity.pdf>, accessed on 23/02/2024.
- [29] EUR-Lex, Regulation (EU) 2018/1139 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2018 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Union Aviation Safety Agency, and amending Regulations (EC) No 2111/2005, (EC) No 1008/2008, (EU) No 996/2010, (EU) No 376/2014 and Directives 2014/30/EU and 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 552/2004 and (EC) No 216/2008 of

the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Regulation (EEC) No 3922/91.

- [30] EASA, The European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS) 2018-2022, 2017, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/EASA%20MB%20Decision%2008-2017%20Annex%201%20EPAS%202018-2022.pdf>, accessed on 22/02/2024.
- [31] J. Anton, "Cybersecurity; an EASA perspective on developments and challenges", online: https://www.iata.org/whatwedo/workgroups/Documents/Paperless_Conference_2017/Day1/1100-1130_Cybersecurity_EASA.pdf, accessed on 23/02/2024.
- [32] J. Rasmussen, EASA, "Conclusions of High Level Cybersecurity Conference", 2020, online: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/newsroom-and-events/events/2020-high-level-cybersecurity-conference>, accessed on 19/05/2024.
- [33] United States Computer Emergency Readiness Team (US-CERT), "Securing Wireless Networks", 2016, online: www.us-cert.gov/ncas/tips/ST05-003, accessed on 19/05/2024.
- [34] T. Hamilton, D. Ochmanek, "Operating Low-Cost, Reusable Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Contested Environments" published by the RAND Corporation, Santa Monica, USA 2020.
- [35] M. Ostrihansky, M. Sakowska-Baryła, M. Szmigiero, The law of drones, Unmanned aircraft in European Union law, Warszawa 2021.
- [36] The National Strategy to Secure Cyberspace [online], February 2003, <http://www.hsd1.org/?view&-did=1040>, accessed on 25/04/2024.
- [37] B. Pacek, R. Hoffman, Działania sił zbrojnych w cyberprzestrzeni, Warszawa 2013.
- [38] E. Nowak, M. Nowak, Zarys teorii bezpieczeństwa narodowego, Warszawa 2011.
- [39] P. Sienkiewicz, H. Świeboda, Sieci teleinformatyczne jako instrument państwa – zjawisko walki informacyjnej, in: Bezpieczeństwo teleinformatyczne państwa.
- [40] E. Lichocki, Model systemu zarządzania kryzysowego w warunkach zagrożeń cyberterrorystycznych dla bezpieczeństwa informacyjnego Sił Zbrojnych RP, Wydział Bezpieczeństwa Narodowego Akademii Obrony Narodowej, Warszawa 2009.
- [41] Aleksandrowicz T., Strategie bezpieczeństwa w cyberprzestrzeni. Cyberwojny, w: Sieciocentryczne bezpieczeństwo. Wojna, pokój i terroryzm w epoce informacji, K. Liedel, P. Piasecka, T. Aleksandrowicz (red.), Warszawa 2014, Difin.

- [42] Konert A., Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne. Nowa era w prawie lotniczym. Zagadnienia cywilnoprawne, C.H. Beck, Warszawa 2020.
- [43] Konert A., Kasprzyk P., Drone Law. Future of Aviation Law?, Peter Lang, 2023.
- [44] Konert A., Kotliński M., "How come I cannot fly with the drone over the White House?" - Criminal and Civil Liability of the Drone Operator in Poland, Ius Novum nr 4/2018.
- [45] Konert A., Kotliński M., Polish regulations on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Transportation Research Procedia Volume 35, 2018.
- [46] Konert A., Odpowiedzialność operatora bezzałogowego statku powietrznego za opóźnienie lub odwołanie lotu, Ius Novum 1/2021.
- [47] Konert A., Przetwarzanie danych osobowych przez operatorów bezzałogowych statków powietrznych, Ius Novum 2/2021.
- [48] Osiecki M., Fortońska A., Książek-Janik E., Criminal liability for unlawful usage of unmanned aircraft vehicles in selected countries of the world. 2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS), 903-910.
- [49] Osiecki M., Fortońska, A., Berus, M. et al. Drone as a Target of Terrorist Attack and a Weapon Against Terrorism – Analysis in the Light of International Law. J Intell Robot Syst 106, 6 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-022-01712-2>.
- [50] Osiecki M., International Legal Aspects of Aerial Terrorism. Methods of Law Enforcement in Aviation, Peter Lang Publishing (2002) Berlin, pp. 86-93.
- [51] Kostur K., Żmigrodzka M., Balcerzak T. (2020), Bezzałogowe statki powietrzne w ochronie przeciwpożarowej, Unmanned aerial vehicles in fire protection, REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVEGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica).
- [52] Pyzynski M., Balcerzak T. (2020), Cybersecurity of the Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS), REVISTA EUROPEA DE DERECHO DE LA NAVEGACIÓN MARÍTIMA YAERONÁUTICA, ISSN (versión electrónica): 2386-8902, ISSN (versión impresa): 1130-2127 Depósito legal: Z-3235-99 Malaga.
- [53] Balcerzak T., Kostur-Balcerzak K., Żmigrodzka M., (2019), Cybersecurity in civil aviation, Bezpieczeństwo w międzynarodowym i krajowym prawie lotniczym i kosmicznym, ISBN: 978-83-7996-752-0.
- [54] Żmigrodzka M. (2022) Opportunities and Threats to Services using Unmanned Aerial Systems, Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews, eISSN2395-6518.